

Scale-Bridging Mechanical Properties of Iron Aluminides

Jan Lars Riedel^a, Alexander Kauffmann^{b*}, Stefan Guth^a, Daniel Schliephake^a, Marcel Münch^a, Georg Winkens^a, Jung Soo Lee^c, James P. Best^c, Frank Stein^c and Martin Heilmaier^a

^a Institute for Applied Materials (IAM), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Engelbert-Arnold-Str. 4, D-76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

^b Institute for Materials (IM), Ruhr University Bochum (RUB), Universitätsstraße 150, D-44780 Bochum, Germany

^c Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials GmbH, Max-Planck-Straße 1, D-40237 Düsseldorf, Germany

* corresponding author

mail: alexander.kauffmann@rub.de (A. Kauffmann)

phone: +49 234 32-18430

Supplementary

Figure S1: The diffraction patterns for all alloys after homogenization at 1000 °C for 48 h (Fe-53Al: 168 h) and 400 °C for 120 h. a) Fe-30Al, b) Fe-35Al, c) Fe-42Al, d) Fe-47Al, e) Fe-50Al, f) Fe-53Al. Downward-facing triangles indicate the respective peaks. The lattice parameter for each alloy is given in the upper left corner of the respective diagrams. Note that the intensity scale is in logarithmic scale.

The ordered structure could not be resolved by XRD measurements for Fe-30Al, as the unit cell of $D0_3$ is twice the size of a $B2$ unit cell and hence, the $B2$ and $D0_3$ peaks could not be differentiated. For Fe-35Al and Fe-42Al the $B2$ -order could not be resolved in XRD as there was no superstructure peak distinguishable from the background noise. Only for Fe-47Al, Fe-50Al and Fe-53Al, a (100)

superstructure peak could be resolved by XRD. No secondary phases were detected in XRD investigations as the volume fraction is below the detection limit.

Figure S2: The microstructure of Fe-53Al after the heat treatment at 400 °C for a duration of 120 h. FeAl₂ is visible as lenticular features within grains and along grain boundaries.

Figure S3: The microstructure of Fe-53Al after casting and after homogenization for 168 h at 1000 °C. The two-phase microstructure is not visible on the macroscale after homogenization. According to the equilibrium phase diagram, there should be still some FeAl₂.

Figure S4: The correlation between nano hardness and 5% offset yield strength. Error bars are within symbol size.

Figure S5: The correlation between Vickers Hardness (HV1) and 5% offset yield strength. Error bars are within symbol size.

Figure S6: a) Representative (selected) true stress-strain curves for Fe-30Al at different temperatures. All shown tests were interrupted at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1) \%$ total strain, indicated by an arrow. b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-30Al deformed at different temperatures. The 1 % offset yield strength R_{p1} is given for the respective temperature as grey lines in the same line style as the testing temperature. The Considère criterion is reached at $\epsilon_t = 15 \%$ at 500 °C, $\epsilon_t = 2 \%$ at 600 °C and $\epsilon_t = 4 \%$ at 700 °C.

Figure S7: a) Representative (selected) true stress-strain curves for Fe-42Al at different temperatures. All shown tests were interrupted at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1)$ % total strain, indicated by an arrow. b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-42Al deformed at different temperatures. The 1 % offset yield strength R_{p1} is given for the respective temperature as grey lines in the same line style as the testing temperature. The Considère criterion is reached at $\epsilon_t = 12$ % at 500 °C, $\epsilon_t = 6$ % at 600 °C and $\epsilon_t = 5$ % at 700 °C.

Figure S8: a) Representative (selected) true stress-strain curves for Fe-47Al at different temperatures. All shown tests were interrupted at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1)$ % total strain, indicated by an arrow. b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-47Al deformed at different temperatures. The 1 % offset yield strength R_{p1} is given for the respective temperature as grey lines in the same line style as the testing temperature. The Considère criterion is reached at $\epsilon_t = 15$ % at room temperature and 400 °C, $\epsilon_t = 7$ % at 500 °C, $\epsilon_t = 3$ % at 600 °C and $\epsilon_t = 3$ % at 700 °C.

Figure S9: a) Representative (selected) true stress-strain curves for Fe-53Al at different temperatures. All shown tests were interrupted at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1) \%$ total strain, indicated by an arrow, except the one at RT because the sample failed, marked by a cross. b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-53Al deformed at different temperatures. The 1 % offset yield strength R_{p1} is given for the respective temperature as grey lines in the same line style as the testing temperature. The Considère criterion is reached at $\epsilon_t = 8 \%$ at room temperature, $\epsilon_t = 7 \%$ at 400°C , $\epsilon_t = 4 \%$ at 500°C , $\epsilon_t = 3 \%$ at 600°C and $\epsilon_t = 2 \%$ at 700°C .

Figure S10: The microstructure of Fe-30Al after deformation at different temperatures. The scale bar is for all images. The compression direction is given in the upper right corner of image a), total strain was 15% for all displayed images. Deformation temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.39 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.45 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.50 \cdot T_S$), e) 700°C ($0.56 \cdot T_S$). Neither intergranular cracking nor the onset of dynamic recrystallization is found at all temperatures.

Figure S11: The microstructure of Fe-42Al after deformation at different temperatures. The scale bar is for all images. The compression direction is given in the upper right corner of image a), total strain was 15% for all displayed images. Deformation temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.41 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.48 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.54 \cdot T_S$), e) 700°C ($0.60 \cdot T_S$). It is seen that intergranular cracking occurs up to 400°C, the onset of dynamic recrystallization is found at 700°C with the typical necklace structure at the grain boundaries.

Figure S12: The microstructure of Fe-7Al after deformation at different temperatures. The scale bar is for all images. The compression direction is given in the upper right corner of image a), total strain was 15% for all displayed images. Deformation temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.43 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.49 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.56 \cdot T_S$), e) 700°C ($0.62 \cdot T_S$). It is seen in the images that intergranular cracking occurs up to 500°C. No indication for the onset of dynamic recrystallization is found at 700°C.

Figure S13: The microstructure of Fe-53Al after deformation at different temperatures. The scale bar is for all images. The compression direction is given in the upper right corner of image a), total strain was 15% for all displayed images except for image a), where the total strain was just 8%. Deformation temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.49 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.57 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.64 \cdot T_S$), e) 700°C ($0.71 \cdot T_S$). It is seen in the images that intergranular cracking occurs up to 400°C. No indication for the onset of dynamic recrystallization is found at 700°C but instead, FeAl₂ segregates to the grain boundary at 600°C and above.

Figure S14: Properties of kink bands for Fe-35Al after deformation at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$. a) region of interest (ROI) as an orientation map (left) with respect to compression direction (the color code of orientations corresponds to the IPF in the inset in the left upper corner) and kernel average misfit (KAM) map of the identical area (right). Black arrows highlight kink bands. b) Misorientation angle distribution along the boundary of one individual kink band highlighted by the red polygon in a). c) Relative frequency distribution of misorientation angles (histogram) from b). A Gauss fit is plotted as line in the diagram. d) Orientation distribution of rotation axes determined from the ROI of b) presented as colored map in an IPF. e) Stereographic projections from the orientations obtained in a) including the possible slip planes (kink band normal) highlighted as black lines. Eulerian angles in Bunge notation.

Figure S15: Properties of kink bands for Fe-35Al after deformation at 600 °C. a) region of interest (ROI) as an orientation map (left) with respect to compression direction (the color code of orientations corresponds to the IPF in the inset in the left upper corner) and kernel average misfit (KAM) map of the identical area (right). Black arrows highlight kink bands. b) Misorientation angle distribution along the boundary of one individual kink band highlighted by the red polygon in a). c) Relative frequency distribution of misorientation angles (histogram) from b). A Gauss fit is plotted as line in the diagram. d) Orientation distribution of rotation axes determined from the ROI of b) presented as colored map in an IPF. e) Stereographic projections from the orientations obtained in a) including the possible slip planes (kink band normal) highlighted as black lines. Eulerian angles in Bunge notation.